

ISic0634

Dedication to Zeus and Tyche

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

limestone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.07 by Prag and checked 2013.09.30, 2017.03.24

Last Change

2020-12-21 - Jonathan Prag made minor edits and added new images

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Found in excavations in the Giardino Spagna necropolis (area of the Umberto I hospital), Siracusa, in 1943; exact findspot not currently localised

Coordinates

37.074295, 15.283237

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 49607

Physical Description

A white limestone altar, finished with a claw chisel on all four sides, with inscription on the front face, a relief of an eagle standing on a thunderbolt on the reverse, mouldings on all four sides form the base and the upper register. The altar is broken/damaged across the top

Dimensions

Height 47.9 cm

Width 40.6 cm

Depth 40.3 cm

Layout

The inscribed field is H 26.5 x W 32.7 with three lines of Greek text

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Carefully carved letters, with minimal use of serifs, most visible on tau and chi; the iota adscript at the end of line 2 is small and mid-line; omicron is rhomboid in form, the hastae of the mu are all angled.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 45-55 mm

Line 2: 45 mm

Line 3: 40-45 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 3: 30 mm

Text

1. Δὶ καὶ

2. Τύχη

3. Μαρκιανός

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation (en)

Markianos (dedicated this) to Zeus and Tyche

Commentary

Bernabo Brea suggested linking this dedication to Cic. Verr.4.119 [<http://data.perseus.org/citations/urn:cts:latinLit:phi0474.phi005.perseus-lat1:2.4.119>] and the quarter of Tyche

Digital identifiers:

TM 644876

PHI 332964

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1994.0757

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0787

undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique.* At 1951.0255a

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 202-203

Manganaro, G. 1994. Culti privati nella Sicilia romana. In Le Bohec, Y.(eds.), *L'Afrique, La Gaule, la religion a l'epoque romaine. Melanges a la memoire de Marcel Le Glay.* Brussels. pp. 831-840. At 839 ph

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-21): ISic0634. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4382695>

Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014